

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Stakeholders' opinions on the agricultural practices applied in wheat cultivation in the Continental area and proposals for improvement

In current years, the development of European agriculture is being restricted by environmental threats linked with conventional farming, intensive tillage and monocropping production. To preserve wheat production and prevent soil degradation, sustainable agricultural practices should be implemented by farmers. However, there is still lack of information about how sustainable agricultural practices can enhance the resilience of farms. In the Continental region, 17 stakeholders with an average age of 45 years collaborated in a survey to identify issues, perspectives, and suggestions. The most serious problems identified were low and variable yields, lack of water during the growing period and high incidences of weeds. In this respect, increasing soil organic matter, improving

biodiversity and reducing the incidence of weeds were the key priorities identified by respondents. Conventional or minimal tillage, addition of organic matter and use of green manures to keep the soil covered with vegetation were proposed by most respondents as the most effective farming practices. In addition, the introduction of crop diversification was supported as an effective strategy to control pests and diseases. However, farmers' lack of knowledge about the efficacy, adaptability, management and cost-effectiveness of these measures could hinder their application. Therefore, there is a need to conduct research and provide advice and information to farmers in order to steer agriculture towards profitable and sustainable production systems.

1. Wheat cultivation in the Continental region

KEYWORDS

Survey, wheat cultivation, Continental region, sustainable production

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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